

APPROACH, METHOD, AND TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract:

Teaching methods are broader techniques used to help students achieve learning outcomes, while activities are the different ways of implementing these methods. Teaching methods help students: master the content of the course. learn how to apply the content in particular contexts. Method is “an overall plan for the orderly presentation of language materials, no part of which contradicts, and all of which is based upon, the selected approach”. Technique is “implementation”, referring to “a particular trick, strategy, or contrivance used to accomplish an immediate objective”.

Key words: The Grammar-Translation Method (GTM), Direct Method, Audiolingual Method, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), Grammar Paraphrasing, indigenous language, Humanistic Approach, Natural Method.

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Exploring English teaching technique used for young learners

This research aims to explore the importance of teaching English to young learners. Currently, English language education is not limited to high schools but also extends to young learners' education, both in Indonesia and in other countries. In fact, it is more advantageous to begin learning English at a young age because young learners are in their golden age, during which their memory is exceptionally sharp, facilitating the memorization and learning of new concepts. Prioritizing English language education for young learners is crucial as it equips children with the proficiency in English language skills required for their education. The research methodology used in this study includes observation, documentation, interviews, and field notes subsequent levels of education.

Evaluation Method of English Distance Teaching Quality in Online Education Platform.

The research methodology used in this study includes observation, documentation, interviews, and field notes. This study suggests the design of evaluation methods for English distance teaching quality in online education platforms in order to increase the accuracy of the evaluation. The method first establishes the selection principle of the quality evaluation index of English distance education, chooses the appropriate quality evaluation index of English distance education, decides on the method of gathering information for the evaluation index, processes the information gathered, and uses the analytic hierarchy process to calculate the weight of the distance education quality evaluation index. Finally, the weighted average method is used to obtain the

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evaluation result of English distance teaching quality, which realizes the evaluation

Review of five methods used in English language teaching

The Grammar-Translation Method (GTM), Direct Method, Audiolingual Method, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) are the five English language teaching modalities that are covered in this review study. An overview of each method's historical context is given before the goals, guiding principles, methods, and constraints are discussed. Because ELT approaches offer instructors a structured framework for efficiently delivering instructions and knowledge, it is imperative that these methods be continuously examined. The choice of teaching technique is crucial to satisfy all the requirements of successful language teaching and learning. Furthermore, various pupils respond better to different learning strategies. Although there are many different teaching techniques available today, this essay will focus on the most important ones that helped shape the field's early years and historical trajectory.

However, for various reasons, there is strong resistance to the complete removal of grammar teaching from foreign language learning syllabuses. Many learners and teachers dislike the absence of grammar teaching in stronger versions of this approach. However, for various reasons, there is strong resistance to the complete removal of grammar teaching from foreign language learning syllabuses. Many learners and teachers dislike the absence of grammar teaching in stronger versions of this approach. While most language teachers and language schools would say that they use a 'communicative' approach, an examination of modern textbooks shows the influence of many different methodologies. The core of most modern textbooks is, in fact, a grammar syllabus rather than a functional syllabus, but plenty of functional/communicative work is included and most teachers would agree that it is important to maximise student-centred activities and reduce teacher-centred teaching.

Primary Methods of Teaching English

Grammar Paraphrasing

This language teaching method is just a classic one, utilized considering that the 16th century. This method ended up being improvised for teaching the Latin language, which was not commonly discovered and spoken by people. The strategy of teaching English focused on translating the texts in Latin to the indigenous language then gaining it, based on the grammatical rules and vocabulary of Latin. The rote learning technique is the most used approach to learn the language. Later on, this method ended up being used to learn other languages. Thus, it pertains to English too. This process does not have in the proven fact that it is not a very good way of teaching to communicate appropriately in English. Though this antique technique has received plenty of critique in our contemporary world, numerous institutions. [1]

Natural Method

This method of teaching English, also known as the direct method, is apparently an answer to the Grammar interpretation method. In this technique, the teacher that is aiming to teach English as being a second language asks the student to think in English so that they can communicate in English.

The strategy is aimed at building a connection between idea and expression. It required the instructor to strictly prohibit the student from utilizing their local

language. The learner is supposed to completely learn in English, with appropriate accent and usage of grammatical skills.

Humanistic Approach

Through the 1970s, teaching and learning course underwent a radical modification where the learner's innate potential and acquired skills were the focal point regarding the training procedure. A couple of training practices were developed centered on this idea, and we were holding grouped underneath the name associated with the humanistic approach. Still utilize it, especially by those who desire to study English.

Some Basic approaches to teaching English in modern times. Task-based approach

The process targets the students want to develop and, it is in line with the idea, exactly why is English taught? Rather than what's shown. Therefore, here the language is learned by doing specific activities and relating English to the daily discussion.

Project-based approach

As a teacher, you will need to consider why your students to learn English. Now keeping their requirements in mind, you will need to create a project. The task may be a role-play or a presentation.

Usage of smartphones in the classroom

Smartphones have grown to be an inescapable part of our presence. It provides numerous crucial tools to pupils such as a dictionary, guide apps, or grammar apps. The one thing is the fact that we ought to guide pupils about

Operative Tips for Teaching English to Beginners

Keep your instructions clear and straightforward. Remember, while giving commands to your students, it must surely be simple and broken down into short sentences. It need not be too formal or courteous. Encourage the learners to listen and then speak. You ought to motivate the students to listen to the pronunciations, pay attention to the grammar, and produce a vocabulary before they start speaking English. Nevertheless, you'll find lots of the learners attempt to begin speaking within the language the moment the classes commence. Keep in mind that the students are fluent in their language

Keep in mind that your students, while talking broken English, will attempt to imagine their language and convert it into English while speaking. Teach them to attempt to keep a flow and rhythm and deal patiently.

Do your homework correctly. When beginning a new class prepare well using the subject and keep many associated activities prepared. Arrange out clearly how you will introduce the topic, break the ice, and make your students express. Teachers are life directors. From years, they have used different methods and styles for teaching. Teaching English to non-native speakers is a challenging one as the language is not familiar to the students. Try to use the best suitable approach so that, the students, as well as the teachers, can enjoy it! [2,1-23]

Language teaching, like most other topics, has encountered a lot of changes. From the conventional ways, it has shifted to role-plays, interactive games, etc. Generally speaking, anything you teach needs to be highly relevant to the students' environment, as they would be the Centre point associated with the teaching and learning process.

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